

Research Article

A Comparative Analysis of In-Process Quality Control Parameters of Pantoprazole Gastro-Resistant Tablets

Anjali Pawar*, Shreya Sabale, Deven Pardeshi, Sneha Vikhe

Pravara Rural College of Pharmacy, Pravaranagar.

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to evaluate and compare the quality control standards of four different brands of pantoprazole gastro-resistant tablets IP 20 mg, which are commonly prescribed by medical practitioners in the surrounding area. **Method:** Four brands, labelled A, B, C, and D, were assessed using various in vitro quality control tests. These tests included physical appearance, thickness measurement, weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration, and dissolution testing. The dissolution test was performed using the USP Paddle II method, and the drug release was analyzed using a UV Spectrophotometer. **Results & Discussion:** Quality control tests were conducted to assess whether the four pantoprazole tablet brands met the required standards. The tests examined parameters, such as weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, disintegration, and dissolution. All four brands (A, B, C, and D) were enteric-coated tablets. When comparing dissolution profiles, Brand A demonstrated a superior drug release of 99.72%, followed by Brand B at 98.41%. Both brands met the Indian Pharmacopoeia standards for drug release. Similarly, Brand D exhibited better drug release (96.23%) than Brand C (92.74%), although both were within acceptable limits as per Indian Pharmacopoeia standards [1][2].

INTRODUCTION

Pantoprazole is an oral route medication falling under proton pump inhibitor (PPI) and completes its action within the gastric cell by reducing the production of gastric acids as per the dosage availability. Moreover, it

acts as an antibacterial agent that inhibits the effects of *Helicobacter pylori* in the stomach. Most reports indicate that pantoprazole tablets are effective and well-tolerated drugs worldwide for the treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), including the management of acid-related disorders and the control and

***Corresponding Author:** Anjali Pawar

Address: Pravara Rural College of Pharmacy, Pravaranagar.

Email ✉: anjalimpawar2002@gmail.com

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treatment of ulcers on the gastroduodenal due to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory diseases (NSAID). Pantoprazole also replaced benzimidazole to inhibit the blocking of the H⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzyme through parietal cells, thus inhibiting the secretion of gastric acid.[5]

Proton-pump inhibitors (PPIs):

Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) inhibit gastric acid production specifically on the H⁺/K⁺-ATPase present in the gastric parietal cell. This involves the absorption of the PPI by the parietal cell. PPIs are weak bases;

thus, protonation occurs in the acidic area of the secretory canaliculus of parietal cells. In secretory canaliculi, the methylsulfinyl group is a highly reactive sulfenamide. The last step is the covalent bonding of the reactive sulfenamide to 2 Cysteine residues of the catalytic subunit of the H⁺/K⁺-ATPase of the proton pump. This leads to the inhibition of acid secretion, followed by an elevation in intragastric pH.[6]

Drug profile:

Chemical structure:

Formula: C₁₆H₁₅F₂N₃O₄S

Molecular weight: 383.37 g/mol

Chemical name: 5-(trifluoromethoxy)-2-[[[3,4-dimethoxy-2-pyridinyl)

Methyl]sulfinyl]-1H-benzimidazole Sesquihydrate.

Appearance: White to off-white powder.

Properties: Freely soluble in water.[7]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials

For comparative evaluation of Pantoprazole Gastro-resistant tablets (20 mg), four tablet brands from different pharmaceutical companies were purchased from the local market: PAN20, Pantop20, Pentab20, and PANTAKIND, and randomly coded as A, B, C, and D, respectively. List of different brands of Pantoprazole tablets and their type are shown in Table 1

Table 1: List Of Different Brands of Pantoprazole Tablets

Sr. No	Brand Name	Pharma companies	Type	Named as
1	PAN20	Alkem Health Science	Enteric Coated	A
2	PANTOP20	Aristo Pharmaceuticals Pvt.Ltd.	Enteric Coated	B
3	PENTAB-20	Alembic Pharmaceuticals Ltd.	Enteric Coated	C
4	PANTAKIND	Mankind Pharma Ltd.	Enteric Coated	D

Table 2: Instruments Used During the Comparative Study

Sr. No.	Equipment's Name	Manufacture	Model
1	Weighing Machine	Contech	CH223
2	Thickness	Mitutoyo	CD-6-ASX
3	Hardness	Orchid	NK-20
4	Friabilator	Electro lab	EF 2L
5	Disintegration	Veego	VTD-D
6	Dissolution	Electrolab	Inspire 8
7	UV Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu	UV-1800

Methods

The four brands designated as A, B, C, and D were subjected to quality control tests as described below.

1. Physical Appearance
2. Weight variation test
3. Thickness test
4. Hardness test
5. Friability test
6. Disintegration test
7. Preparation of Standard Calibration curve
8. Dissolution test carried out using the USP Paddle II method and analysed using a UV Spectrophotometer.[8][9]

1. Physical Appearance

The color and shape of the tablets were observed with the naked eye to verify their uniformity. Some companies have added grooves to the tablet surface to identify their brands. All of these features were determined through visual inspection.

1. Weight variation test

A weight variation test was conducted to ensure uniformity of the tablet weights. The weight of a

tablet corresponds to the amount of medicinal component it contains. To verify consistency, tablet weights were frequently tested after manufacturing. In this study, 20 tablets were randomly selected and weighed. The average weight was calculated to determine the standard weight of a single tablet. The weight of each tablet was recorded individually and deviations from the acceptable weight range were noted. The standard limits of weight variation are listed in Table 3.[10]

Table 3: Standard Specifications of Weight Variation Tests

Sr. No.	Average wt. of tablets(mg)	Max.% Difference allowed
1.	84 or less	10%
2.	84 -250	7.5%
3.	More than 250	5%

2. Thickness

Digital Vernier calipers were used to measure the tablet thickness. This provides information regarding the variation between tablets and provides precise measurements. Average results were determined using ten tablets.[10]

3. Hardness test

The hardness of tablets determines their resistance to capping, abrasion, or breakage during handling, storage, and transit before use. The load necessary to break or fracture a tablet resting on its edge is known as tablet hardness. This is occasionally referred to as the pillar crushing strength. Five tablets of each brand were ingested, and pressure was applied while the tablet was positioned between the spindles of the hardness tester. Then, the pressure was raised as gradually as possible until the tablet broke, the amount of pressure needed to do so was recorded and read from the device, and the hardness tester's sliding scale was

calibrated to zero. I.P. states that the range is 4– 8 kg/cm². [11]

4. Friability test

The friability test for pantoprazole tablets determines tablet strength by evaluating the weight loss under pressure in a friabilator. Because pantoprazole tablets are enteric-coated tablets, they were weighed, rotated 100 times at 25 rpm, and then reweighed; the permissible level was ≤1%. [11]

5. Disintegration Time

The disintegration time test was performed as per the specifications. First, the disintegration tester was filled with 0.1N HCl and maintained at 37±2°C. Then, it was run for 2 h after placing six randomly selected tablets from each pantoprazole brand in the disintegration tester. Tablets were examined for signs of disintegration within 2 hrs running period. By changing the acidic fluid with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8 immediately after 2 h, the apparatus was operated for an additional 1 h at 37±2°C, and the disintegration time was noted. The tablets were considered completely disintegrated when all the particles passed through the wire mesh. [12]

7. Standard calibration curve

1. Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

Pantoprazole sodium (10 mg) was accurately weighed using an analytical balance and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. The drug was dissolved in 100 mL of 0.1N HCl (or methanol, depending on solubility requirements) and sonicated if necessary for complete dissolution. The volume was made up to 100 mL using the same solvent to obtain a 100 µg/mL stock solution.

2. Preparation of Working Standard Solutions

Different concentrations were prepared from the stock solution by dilution with Phosphate Buffer (pH 6.8) to obtain concentrations of 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 µg/mL.

3. Measurement of Absorbance

The absorbance of each prepared concentration was recorded using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at the maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) of pantoprazole (usually approximately 294 nm, but should be determined experimentally). A blank solution (Phosphate Buffer, pH 6.8) was used for the baseline correction.

4. Plotting the Calibration Curve

A calibration curve was plotted by taking the concentration (µg/mL) on the X-axis and the absorbance on the Y-axis. A linear regression equation was derived to determine the correlation coefficient (R^2) and to ensure good linearity. [14][15]

8. Dissolution Study

Gastro-resistant (enteric-coated) tablets of pantoprazole sodium are dissolved in the intestine, where absorption takes place, avoiding stomach breakdown. To replicate the physiological conditions, a two-stage dissolving test was performed:

1. Acid Stage: Maintains the integrity of the enteric coating (0.1N HCl, pH 1.2).
2. Alkaline stage: Assess drug release under intestinal conditions using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

Reagents and Materials

- 20 mg gastro-resistant tablets of pantoprazole sodium
- 0.1N HCl (0.1N hydrochloric acid; pH 1.2)
- pH 6.8 phosphate buffer
- UV-visible spectrophotometer
- USP Type II (Paddle) Dissolution Apparatus
- Glassware:
Pipettes Methodology of Volumetric Flasks (1000 mL, 100 mL)

Phase 1: Acidic (pH 1.2, 0.1N HCl) Two hours

Procedure

1. Dissolution Medium: Add 750 mL of 0.1N HCl to each dissolution vessel.
2. Temperature Control: Maintain at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.
3. Stirring conditions: The paddle speed was set at 50 rpm.
4. Tablet placement One pantoprazole gastro-resistant tablet (20 mg) was placed in each vessel.
5. Sampling: Ten millilitres of the sample was withdrawn at 60, 90, and 120 min.
6. Filtration: The samples using a 0.45 μm membrane filter.
7. Analysis: Absorbance was measured using UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 290 nm.
8. Acceptance Criteria: No 10% of the drug should be dissolved in this phase, confirming that the enteric coating remains intact.

Stage 2: Alkaline Phase (pH 6.8 Phosphate Buffer) – Until Complete Dissolution

Procedure

1. Medium Replacement: After 2 h, the acidic medium was removed and replaced with 1000 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).
2. Temperature Control: Maintain at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.
3. Stirring conditions: the paddle speed was maintained at 50 rpm.
4. Sampling: Ten milliliters of the sample was withdrawn at 10, 20, 30, 45, and 60 min.
5. Filtration: The withdrawn samples using a 0.45 μm membrane filter.
6. Analysis: Absorbance was measured using UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 290 nm.
7. Acceptance Criteria: At least 80% of the drug should be dissolved within 60 min in phosphate buffer.[13]

RESULTS

1. Physical Appearance

The color, surface, and shape of the tablets were visually inspected. The physical appearances of the different pantoprazole brands are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Physical characteristics of Pantoprazole tablet

Sr. No.	Brands	Color	Shape	Surface
1	A	Brown	Round	Smooth
2	B	Orange	Round	Smooth
3	C	Yellow	Round	Smooth
4	D	Yellow	Round	Smooth

2. Weight Variation Test

A weight variation test was conducted to assess the uniformity of tablet weight in accordance with pharmaceutical standards. A random sample of 20

(n = 20) pantoprazole tablets (20 mg) was selected and individually weighed using a calibrated analytical balance. Average weight was determined by dividing the total weight of the

sample by 20. The weight variation of the tablets was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Upper Limit} = \text{Average Weight} + (7.5/100 \times \text{Average weight})$$

$$\text{Lower Limit} = \text{Average Weight} - (7.5/100 \times \text{Average weight})$$

According to USP/BP guidelines, tablets with an average weight between 80 and 250 mg must not deviate beyond $\pm 7.5\%$ of the mean weight. The batch was considered acceptable if no more than two tablets exceeded this limit and none deviated beyond $\pm 15\%$. This test ensures consistency in

tablet weight, which is critical for maintaining a uniform drug content and efficacy.

Table 5: Calculations and results of weight variation

Brands	Upper Limit(gm)	Lower Limit(gm)	Result
A	0.211	0.182	Comply
B	0.202	0.179	Comply
C	0.118	0.101	Comply
D	0.170	0.147	Comply

Fig. 2: Weight Variation of Diff. Brands

3. Thickness

The thicknesses of different brands of Pantoprazole Tablets (20 mg) were determined using a digital Vernier caliper, and the results are listed in Table 6.

Table 6: Individual thickness of tablets and results

Sr. No.	Brand A	Brand B	Brand C	Brand D
1	4.00	3.52	3.11	3.60

2	3.95	3.48	3.13	3.68
3	4.03	3.45	3.11	3.69
4	3.87	3.48	3.12	3.63
5	4.03	3.52	3.02	3.65
6	3.99	3.52	3.17	3.66
7	3.98	3.45	3.18	3.66
8	4.01	3.56	3.12	3.59
9	3.99	3.50	3.14	3.76

10	3.91	3.47	3.07	3.59
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Average	3.976m m	3.495m m	3.117m m	3.651m m
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Graphical Representations of The Average Thicknesses of The Individual Brands Are Shown In Fig 3.

4. Hardness

The hardness of the different brands of pantoprazole tablets (10 mg) was determined using a digital hardness tester, and the results are listed in Table 7.

1	5.4	5.3	5.5	5.2	4 to 10 kg/c m ²
2	5.7	5.9	5.0	4.9	
3	5.9	5.8	5.9	4.9	
4	5.6	5.4	5.8	5.4	
5	6.0	5.9	5.7	5.1	
Average	5.72	5.66	5.58	5.1	
Result	Comply	Comply	Comply	Comply	

Table 7: Hardness of tablets and results

Sr. No.	Hardness of tablets (kg/cm ²)				Std
	A	B	C	D	

Fig. 4 Hardness of Diff. Brands of Tablets

5. Friability Test

The friability of the different brands of Pantoprazole Tablets (10 mg) was determined

using Roche Friability instruments for 4 min at 25 rpm, and the results are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Friability of tablets

	% Friability of tablets				Std. 0.5 to 1 % acc. to I.P
	A	B	C	D	
Initial Wt.	3.967	3.847	2.216	3.216	
Final Wt.	3.963	3.844	2.213	3.214	
% Friability	0.100	0.077	0.135	0.0621	
Result	Comply	Comply	Comply	Comply	

A graphical presentation of the friability of the individual brands is shown in Fig 5.

Fig. 5: Friability of diff. brands

6. In Vitro Disintegration Test

The test for decomposition time was performed according to the specifications. First, the disintegration tester was filled with 0.1 N HCl and maintained at 37 ± 2 °C. It was also run for 2 h

after placing the six tablets from each pantoprazole brand in the decomposition tester. Tablets were examined for signs of decomposition within 2 hrs running period. By changing the acidic fluid with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8 incontinently after 2 h, the outfit was operated for 1 h at 37 ± 2 °C, and the

decomposition time was noted. The tablets were considered fully disintegrated when all the patches passed through the line mesh.

Table 9: Disintegration of tablets

Product	Disintegration time in 0.1N HCL (min)	Disintegration time in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer (min)
Brand A	No evidence of disintegration for 2 hr.	16.32
Brand B	No evidence of disintegration for 2 hr.	19.43
Brand C	No evidence of disintegration for 2 hr.	24.15
Brand D	No evidence of disintegration for 2 hr.	20.32

7. Standard Calibration Curve for Pantoprazole

The calibration curve of the standard was drawn by plotting the Absorbance against Concentration. Figure 7 shows the standard calibration curves. A correlation coefficient greater than 0.9999 reflected the occurrence of homogeneity in the concentration range of 0 – 10µg/ml. The absorbance of the Pantoprazole tablet was Measurements were performed using a UV spectrophotometer (Table 10).

Table 10: Absorbance determined by UV Spectrophotometer

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (%)
1	0	0
2	2	0.211
3	4	0.418
4	6	0.625
5	8	0.831
6	10	1.032

Fig. 7: UV estimation of Pantoprazole

8. In Vitro Dissolution Study

The results of in vitro dissolution studies are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Dissolution time and % drug release in 0.1% HCL

Time	Pan20	Pantop20	Pantab-20	Pantakind
0	0	0	0	0
60	3.357	3.226	2.485	2.354
90	5.101	4.97	3.793	4.098
120	7.281	6.715	4.665	5.843

Fig. 8: Cumulative % drug release in 0.1N HCL media

Table 12: Dissolution Time And % Drug Release in Phosphate Buffer Ph 6.8

Time	Pan20	Pantop20	Pantab-20	Pant kind
120	0	0	0	0
130	31.246	28.212	21.671	33.008
140	44.345	40.421	46.09	45.218
150	77.049	73.997	67.02	69.636
165	89.694	86.206	79.665	83.154
180	99.723	98.415	92.747	96.235

Fig. 9: Cumulative % drug release in phosphate Buffer

DISCUSSION:

Quality control parameters of different brands of marketed pantoprazole tablets with Indian pharmacopeia standards.

All four brands' pantoprazole tablets were according to IP standards found to be within $\pm 7.5\%$ of the average weight of the tablets. All four brands performed within the specified ranges. The results show that brand A has more weight variation than brand B, and brand D has more weight variation than brand C (Fig 2). This could be attributed to the lower powder flowability under compression. The range of hardness is from 4 to 10 kg/cm². Based on hardness tests, the average hardness values for Brands A and B are 5.72 kg/cm² and 5.66 kg/cm², respectively, whereas the average hardness values of Brands C and D are 5.58 kg/cm² and 5.1 kg/cm², respectively (table 7). This shows that both brands are acceptable in the hardness test as all four Hardness values are less than the pharmacopeia limit. The pharmacopeia mentions that a 0.5 % tablet loss during shipping is acceptable, and the friability equipment utilized in this friability test shows that the friability test was successful for all four tablet brands. The disintegration test of pantoprazole tablets was conducted in 0.1N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8. In 0.1N HCl, no tablets disintegrated, which shows successful enteric coating intended to withstand acidic environments. In phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), the tablets disintegrated at different times: Brand A (16.32 min), Brand B (19.43 min), Brand D (20.32 min), and Brand C (25.15 min). The fastest disintegration was shown by Brand A, and the slowest was shown by Brand C, indicating differences in coating thickness or efficiency in the formulation. These differences might affect the release and efficacy of the drug. The dissolution profiles of four pantoprazole tablet brands (A, B, C, and

D) were compared. The experiment was carried out using USP Type II apparatus in 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with the drug release determined by UV spectrophotometry. The results indicated that Brand A released the most drug (99.72%), followed by Brand B (98.41%), Brand D (96.23%), and Brand C (92.74%). Although all brands satisfied pharmacopeial standards, variations in dissolution rates can influence therapeutic effectiveness.

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